

Calling Out of the Grave of Death

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The desperate dance of death and the search for meaningfulness in life haunts the whole world today. We are standing before the Crucified Lord trying to understand what He wishes to reveal to us during this season of the True Lent in our lives. There is real Gethsemane, real Way of the Cross, real Suffering and real Death everywhere. How does it make sense? How and where do we see the ray of hope? When will we be really able to sing Hosanna, Alleluia, He is Risen?

The present world that is infected by the virus, is being sent, day by day, person by person, country by country into the Grave of Death. But our Lord is more powerful than the power of evil and death. The Lord is calling us out of the Grave of Death to the Grace of Depth.

To Live as God's People

Today more than ever before, we feel the need to see the face of Jesus, to feel His presence, to experience His power. It becomes our intense prayer that the Lord our God may let God's face shine upon us; that God may help us to experience God's promises fulfilled, just as the people of God experienced in the old times, just as the beloved of Jesus experienced in the time

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of God in solidarity with God's people, God the Immanuel – God who saves – Jesus our Lord.

We are created to live. It is the promise of God that in the midst of adversity, God will be closer to us, leading us to fullness of life. The imageries of 'Waters', 'Burning Bush', the 'Valley of Bones' and the 'Grave of Lazarus' symbolize paradoxically adversity in the life of the people of God and God's protecting and life-giving presence in their midst.

The 'Waters' of the great flood due to the rain for forty days and forty nights swelled on the earth for one hundred fifty days. But God remembered Noah and every creature that was 'in the ark of God'. It is God's promise that never again will God destroy living creatures (Gen 7-9). Only condition is that we respond to the invitation of God to "go into our ark" in these troubled times. The 'Burning Bush' signifies God's burning love for the suffering people of God: "I have observed the misery of my people... I have heard their cry... I know their sufferings, and I have come down to deliver them..." (Ex 3). It is God's promise that in the midst of hopelessness God will cause breath to enter the dead bones in the Valley of dry Bones and they shall live and He shall be their God and they shall be His people (Ezek 37).

It is the will of God that we live and become God's people. God wants to bring us out from the troubled waters in our time to new life, from our misery, suffering and death to experience freedom and prosperity, from the valley of bones to life in its fullness. Jesus comes to give us that fullness of life. He has come to call us out of our graves, to transform us from dry bones into a new creation. The imagery of the 'Grave of Lazarus' (Jn 11) is an assurance of this truth. Jesus is the Resurrection and Life; Jesus is the Messiah, the

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Son of God; and everyone who lives and believes in Jesus will never die. Those who trust like Lazarus – God is my help – will hear the life giving voice of the Lord: Lazarus come out!

Sharing the Burden of Each Other: From the Grave of Death to the Grace of Depth.

As followers of Christ, we are called to take away the burden from the lives of people and lead them to total freedom from sin, sickness and suffering, unbound them from the clutches of death in order to experience life in Christ. With our help, the Lord wants to call the many dead Lazarus back to life. We could do this with patience, faith and prayer in our troubled time, when many of us think that God is absent, indifferent and sleeping.

The meditation of Pope Francis on 27th March 2020 during the prayer service on the steps of St Peter's Basilica, invites us to echo the words of the panicked Disciples: "Lord we are perishing, do you not care for us?" (Mk 4:38). Is Jesus sleeping in our turbulent times? Many of us think it so. But He is there with us in the ark of our life. He would not let it sink. Do not be afraid. Have faith.

In the words of Pope Francis: "We have an anchor: by His Cross we have been saved. We have a rudder: by His Cross we have been redeemed. We have a hope: by His Cross we have been healed and embraced so that nothing and no one can separate us from His redeeming love."

We focus our attention on the Crucified Lord who confined Himself to the Tomb in order to draw us out of death. We spend time in the presence of the Lord, with depth, silence and prayer, remaining in the tomb created by the virus of

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He has overcome death and has made for us Resurrection possible. Believe and we shall live and shall sing meaningfully Hosanna,

death. We go into our ark and listen to Him in the depth of misery and death. He is calling us out of the Grave of Death to the Grace of Depth.

The Empty Tomb

In the midst of all these images, one image stands out: The Empty TOMB. It is only after the grain of wheat dies, that it would produce much fruit. Through the passage that goes through the empty

tomb does one enter into life. The empty tomb assures us that HE is not there in the midst of the dead. HE IS RISEN and is calling us out of our graves, leading us from darkness to Light, from untruth to Truth, from death to Life. Now it is the Emmaus time, a time to encounter the Risen Lord in spite of death and despair, loneliness and hopelessness, to let Him walk with us while it is getting dark, to let Him open to us the scripture and make our hearts burning with Hope, Optimism and Peace, to see Him in His Glory with our own eyes in the midst of the dance of death. It is a time to return to our people, like the Disciples on the way to Emmaus, to proclaim to them that the Lord is risen, death is defeated, new life has sprouted. The Risen Lord is inviting us to return back to Him in the depth of our being, asking us to listen to and respond to the voice that invites us to be co-creators, compassionate Healers, and Messengers of Hope.

Conclusion

Let us continue to respond with faith, patience and courage from the depth of our being till our world becomes the Promised reality – A New Heaven and a New Earth – where every tear will be wiped

away – death will be defeated and we shall experience the fullness of life. That is why He has come. He has overcome death and has made for us Resurrection possible. Believe and we shall live and shall sing meaningfully Hosanna, Alleluia, He is Risen!!!

“We have an anchor: by His Cross we have been saved. We have a rudder: by His Cross we have been redeemed. We have a hope: by His Cross we have been healed and embraced so that nothing and no one can separate us from His redeeming love.” – Pope Francis